

HYGROTHERMAL AGING AND DURABILITY OF UNIDIRECTIONAL GLASS - EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effects of hygrothermal aging on the fatigue properties of an unidirectional glass/epoxy composite have been investigated. Damage nucleation was monitored in terms of fibre breakage by in-situ microscopic observation of the tensile face of the specimens during flexural tests. The decrease in the endurance properties of the composite after water aging has been found to be related to a drop in the in-situ fibre strength. This fibre weakening may be associated to an increase in the pH of the aging media due to the leaching of an unreacted hardener during the water sorption steps.

INTRODUCTION

In the course of normal service life, structural composites are subjected to both mechanical loading and environmental exposures including at least temperature and humidity. As a result, extensive studies have been carried out over the past few years on the environmental effects on composite materials. A great deal of experimental evidence has been adduced to demonstrate that hygrothermal aging strongly affected both physico-chemical and thermomechanical properties of composites. During water exposure, three major kinds of aging processes may occur :

- reversible plasticisation of the epoxy network resulting from water diffusion [1],
- macroscopical damage such as matrix cracking and/or fibre/matrix debonding which could arise from irreversible chemical degradation or swelling stresses [2],
- loss of bearing properties of the glass reinforcement due to chemical attack in moist environments. This effect is generally attributed to flaw creation on the glass surface due to a thermally activated ion exchange mechanism [3]. Such a process has been also found to be pH sensitive. It is therefore of importance to evaluate the strength of the glass fibres in an physico-chemical environment similar to this encountered in the composite matrix.

However, relatively few studies concern environmental effects on fatigue properties in relation to aging mechanisms. This study was hence directed towards a better understanding of the aging mechanisms in relation to their interactions with fatigue damage initiation and growth. A special emphasis was put on the weakening of the glass fibres in relation physico-chemical changes which can occur in the aging environment or at the fibre/matrix interface. Two complementary means of assessment were thus chosen:

- an approach focused on the physico-chemical changes induced by water uptake,
- a mechanical study of the coupling effects between environment and fatigue which have been investigated via both dynamic and monotonic tests. In-situ microscopic damage mapping was carried out in order to relate the changes in fatigue properties to the in-situ distribution of fibre strength after water aging.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

The material used in this work was an E-glass-epoxy unidirectional laminate with an epoxy matrix based on Bisphenol A hardened by Dicyandiamide (DICY). Plates were obtained by compression moulding of prepregs using a specific cure cycle of 5 minutes at 165°C followed by a 2 h postcure at 140°C. This procedure resulted in a fully crosslinked network with a T_g transition at 150°C measured by DMTA at 1 Hz. Two sample thicknesses were used for the physico-chemical (1 mm) and the mechanical (3 mm) studies. Slightly different volume fractions were achieved depending on the specimen thickness (0.61% for 1mm and 0.55% for 3 mm).

ENVIRONMENTAL EXPOSURE

The material was by immersion in distilled water at four different temperatures, namely 50°C, 60°C, 70°C and 90°C. The effect of environment on flexural fatigue was studied on samples immersed for 340 days in distilled water at 60°C.

Prior to moisture exposure, the as-cast specimens were dried in a vacuum oven at 50°C until they reached constant weight. This state was used as the reference for the measurement of the relative weight gains M_t of the aged specimens. Gravimetric analysis of moisture uptake was monitored by weighing the samples to within 0.1 mg using an analytical balance.

During water aging, UV spectrophotometry was used to investigate the occurrence of some leaching of low molecular weight products such as the unreacted hardener. The UV analysis was performed between 190 nm and 380 nm using UVIKON 941 plus spectrophotometer. The aging medium was analysed with no further preparation. This UV analysis was also associated with pH measurements of the aging solutions.

MONOTONIC TESTS

Monotonic properties were measured before and after aging using a three point bending test. A span to depth ratio of 20 was selected to minimise shear stress and the specimens were loaded at 2 mm.min⁻¹. *In situ* microscopic observation of the tensile face of the specimens was also performed during testing using an optical device linked to a camera and Quantitative Analysis Software. This allowed the detection and location of fibre breakage on an area of 5 x 2 mm² located beneath the loading nose. The following specific loading procedure was used to monitor fibre breakage: The samples were loaded up to successive strain levels. At each strain step, the tensile face of the specimen was scanned using the microscopical device which was moved by a micropositioning unit. This took approximately 10 minutes. The tests were stopped when macroscopic cracks appeared due to the fact that it was no longer possible to identify all the fibre breaks.

DYNAMIC FATIGUE TESTS

The flexural fatigue behaviour of the composite was investigated using a three-point-bending device. Test were conducted at imposed deflection. The frequency was set to 25 Hz to avoid extra heating of the sample. The ratio of minimum strain ϵ_{\min} to maximum strain ϵ_{\max} was chosen as $R = 0.1$. Continuous recording of stiffness loss during the fatigue tests provided damage monitoring. Final breakage of the specimen into two parts is generally not observed during bending fatigue as opposed to during tensile fatigue. A 10% stiffness loss was therefore selected as a conventional failure criterion. The conclusions of this study will, however, remain the same whatever the criterion chosen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SORPTION BEHAVIOUR

The sorption behaviour of the composite immersed in distilled water is shown on Fig. 1. The relative weight gain M_t is plotted versus the square root of immersion time normalised to the thickness h of the sample. After a rapid increase in weight gain at shorter immersion times, slow changes in M_t can be noted at longer times. At 70°C and 90°C, the slight decrease in M_t for long exposure times indicates that some leaching of material components, such as low molecular species, occurred during aging. Whatever the aging temperature, no saturation level can thus be detected. Such a non-Fickian sorption behaviour can be considered as a classical feature of epoxy networks crosslinked with DICY [4]. It has previously been found to be associated to some leaching of unreacted DICY remaining as hygroscopic clusters in the matrix after curing [5].

Figure 1. Sorption behaviour of the composite immersed in distilled water.
(Δ 50°C; \diamond 60°C, \square 70°C, \circ 90°C)

For the composite studied, the occurrence of such a leaching has been investigated using UV analysis of the aging media. Whatever the aging temperature, the spectra revealed the progressive appearance of an absorption peak located at 215 nm which is characteristic of DICY hardener in aqueous solution. This wavelength was used to measure DICY concentration versus aging time. The results shown on Fig. 2 revealed that the amount of leached DICY was strongly dependent on the immersion temperature. They can represent up to 0.14 % of the initial weight of the specimens aged at 90°C. The weight loss recorded on the sorption curves therefore include a component related to the leaching of the unreacted hardener. It is hence clear that M_t is only a global parameter which takes into account both water sorption and hardener leaching .

DICY leaching in the aging solutions has also been found to induce a strong increase in pH with respect to exposure time (Fig. 2). Such a process can be attributed to the basic characteristics of the DICY or to amine derivatives resulting from its chemical degradation. It can also be noted that this pH increase is enhanced at elevated temperatures. This may be related either to the higher DICY concentration measured at these temperatures and/or to a higher hydrolysis rate of this product. pH values up to 10 can be obtained in the case of the aging at 90°C after only a few days. Such an observation is of importance since silicate networks are especially known to suffer substantial hydrolysis when pH values exceed 9 [6]. This must be borne in mind when considering the decrease in glass fibre strength which could result from these processes. One can, however, consider a continuous renewal of the distilled water to suppress this pH increase. It will however remain obviously inefficient in avoiding the appearance of a basic environment in

clusters or microvoids inside the composite material, especially at the interface where hydrothermally induced debonding can occur.

Figure 2. Changes in DICY concentration and pH in the aging media versus immersion time. (pH 50°C, pH 90°C, Dicy 50°C, Dicy 90°C)

MONOTONIC PROPERTIES AND DAMAGE ANALYSIS

The residual monotonic properties of the composite were measured after aging 340 days at 60°C. A strong decrease in strain and stress to failure may be noted as shown in Table 1. This effect was further investigated by the analysis of the damage processes during monotonic loading.

Table 1. Ultimate bending properties of the composite before and after aging at 60°C

Aging conditions	Strain to failure ϵ_R (%)
non aged	3.6
immersion at 60°C	1.7

Non aged Material During monotonic loading, the first nucleated defects in the non aged material consisted in broken fibres (Picture 1).

Picture 1. view of a broken fibre with interfacial debonding at fibre tips (non aged composite; magnification x10).

Due to shear stress concentrations, some fibre/matrix debonding can also be identified from the black borders surrounding the broken ends of the fibres. Stress concentrations at the vicinity of the fibre breaks often resulted in the nucleation of matrix cracks. Crack propagation from such a single defect was not observed.

The number of broken fibres detected on the tensile face of the specimens was mapped for increasing strain levels (Fig. 3). At lower strain levels, the broken fibres were randomly distributed on the tensile side of the specimens and were non-interactive. Close to the failure strain level, these defects coalesced and gave way to macroscopic cracks which propagated through the specimen thickness. An average concentration of broken fibres as a function of the applied strain could be derived from this mapping. The results plotted on Fig. 4 show that, due to the statistical distribution of the fibre strength, fibre breakage initiates at strain levels well below the ultimate properties of the material.

Figure 3. Mapping of fibre breaks on the tensile face of a non aged specimen as a function of the applied strain

((a) 50 % ϵ_R ; (b) 60 % ϵ_R ; (c) 80 % ϵ_R)

Material aged at 60°C After aging at 60°C, a shift of the in-situ fibre strength to low strain levels can be noted. It can be noted that the decrease in in-situ fibre strength and failure strain of the composite occurred roughly to the same extent.

Moreover, no interfacial debonding was detected as in the case of the unaged material. This may be due to extensive interfacial degradation which has led to fibre matrix/debonding well beyond the observation area. Rather than containing cracks that extended into the matrix, as for non aged specimens, the broken ends of the fibres were located in a columnar shaped crack. This columnar fragment appeared to contain all the cracks, yielding, debonding and/or fibre pull-out at the interfacial region.

Figure 4. Density of fibre breaks versus the applied strain (monotonic loading, □ non aged, ■ aged in immersion at 60°C)

DYNAMIC FATIGUE

Whatever the environmental conditioning, the analysis of the stiffness loss curves recorded during fatigue tests revealed that the fatigue life can be divided into two steps (fig.5):

i) During the first step, no significant stiffness loss is recorded. This step can be related to the random nucleation of first defects (fibre breaks) on the tensile face of the specimens. From the fibre breakage maps reported in Fig. 3, it can be established that fibre breaking occurred during the first loading the fatigue strain range considered. Due to delayed fracture and stress redistribution, the density of these non interactive defects will progressively increase with time. The number of broken fibres remains, however, insufficient to induce measurable stiffness loss.

Fig. 5 Typical stiffness loss curve recorded during a fatigue test. (non aged material; $\epsilon_{max} = 2.1\%$)

ii) Above a critical density of broken fibres, the nucleated defects coalesce and give way to progressive macroscopic crack propagation. As a result, a continuous stiffness loss is recorded during this second step.

All the fatigue results have been reported on an S-N diagram giving the maximum applied strain ϵ_{max} versus lifetime N_{10} (Fig.6). It can be noted that aging at 60°C resulted in a drop in the endurance properties of the composite. This decrease may be interpreted by two effects :

Figure 6. S-N plots with Wöhler curves for a N10 criterion (□ non aged, ■ aged in immersion at 60°C)

i) an increase in the density of the early nucleated defects due to the reduced in-situ strength properties of the glass fibres (see Fig. 4). As a result, the critical density for macroscopic cracking will be achieved more rapidly. Some indication of this effect may be judged from the reduction in the number of cycles N_s for which the onset in stiffness loss occurred (Table 2.) are

i) As far as the crack propagation rates is concerned, opposed effects must be taken into account. At first, hygrothermally induced debonding at the end of the broken fibres will allow stress relaxation. It can thence be supposed to have beneficial effects on crack propagation. Secondly, the hygrothermally induced flaws will increase the probability to find a defect on the glass fibres located at the crack tip. As a result, crack propagation rates will increase. From the measured values of the difference $N_{10}-N_s$ (Table 2.), one may suppose the later effect to dominate the cracking step.

Table 2. Average values of the initiation and propagation times for the two aging conditions.

Aging condition	ϵ_{max} (%)	N_s	$N_{10} - N_s$
non aged	2.4	1.3 E4	3.6 E5
	2.1	6.6 E4	3.8 E6
	1.4	3.3 E5	2.2 E7
aged at 60°C in immersion	1.5	2.7 E4	1.5 E6
	1.25	3.4 E4	1.1 E7

CONCLUSIONS

Hygrothermal aging of the composite studied has been found to induce substantial drop in the endurance properties during fatigue loading. It has been related to a strong decrease in fibre strength which may be measured by in-situ mapping of fibre breakage during monotonic loading. As a result, higher densities of early nucleated defects are achieved during the first fatigue loading. This affected both the time for the onset of crack propagation and the subsequent crack propagation rates. The detrimental effect of moisture on the load bearing ability of the glass fibres is probably enhanced by pH increase as noted during the water sorption steps. The latter was related to leaching of the unreacted DICY hardener remaining in the composite after curing. Such a process is of importance when considering the local pH increase which can occur at water clusters or hygrothermally induced microvoids at the fibre/matrix interface.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to express appreciation to RENAULT for sponsoring the work presented herein. Many thanks are also addressed to R. Lambrech for carefully revising the English version of this manuscript.

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